

A photograph of an offshore wind farm at sea. The sun is shining brightly in the sky, creating a lens flare effect. Several wind turbines are visible, with the largest one in the foreground on the right. The water is blue and slightly choppy.

Task 52 General Meeting

Wind Lidar: Large-Scale Deployment of Wind Lidar

Operating Agents [OA] (Task Managers):
Julia Gottschall – *Fraunhofer IWES*

Introducing Working Group 9 — Floating LiDAR
O.Sargin - 23.09.2025, Kassel

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Background

FLS have matured over the last decade, enabling offshore wind measurements without fixed masts.

Resources

Access cloud-based workspaces, shared spreadsheets, transcriptions and prior research.

Expectations

Engage actively in discussions, refine priority topics and contribute to concise documents.

Methods

Utilise monthly calls, Teams polls and asynchronous collaboration to reach consensus.

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Participants, Mission & Preliminary Objectives

- **TRL & Bankability:** Assess maturity of 'Stage 3' FLS and criteria for bankable operations.
- **Data Quality Requirements:** Define consensus on availability and accuracy.
- **Campaign Design:** Recommend scope and duration for robust resource assessment.
- **Technology & Machine Learning:** Identify limits and evaluate ML for FLS processing.
- **Uncertainty Benchmarking:** Compare FLS-derived uncertainty with reanalysis; agree acceptable levels.

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The interests driving WG9

Technology & ML in Practice

- Evidence-led innovation & guardrails
- Firmware/signal processing insights
- ML-assisted reviewing; TI transfer functions

Data Quality & Standardization

- QC protocol & shared terminology
- Align with IEC 61400-50-4 & 50-x suite
- Reduce interpretation risk across regions

Uncertainty & Bankability

- Clear, defensible uncertainty statements
- Distinguish measurement vs modelling
- Link uncertainty to asset value

Campaign Design & Metocean Context

- Vertical coherence & sea state
- Regional realities: North Sea ↔ Japan
- Practical recommendations, quantity and scope

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Get involved / our path forward

Next steps: Monthly online sessions; concise documents per topic; open review window.

Timeline: Kick-off Aug 2025 → ...
Dissemination Mar–Apr 2026.

Thank you —
Questions?

Kick-off

Aug 2025

Scoping

Sep 2025

Knowledge Gathering

Oct 2025–Feb 2026

Consensus & Validation

Mar 2026

Dissemination

Late Mar–Apr 2026

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